

SCALING-UP PRACTICAL TEACHING: THE ONE-THOUSAND STUDENT WEEK

M Di Benedetti¹

The University of Sheffield
Sheffield, U.K.
0000-0001-7870-1323

H Day

The University of Sheffield
Sheffield, U.K.
0000-0002-1520-6410

S Archibald

The University of Sheffield
Sheffield, U.K.

Conference Key Areas: *Physics and Engineering Education; Curriculum Development, Engineering Skills, Lifelong Learning.*

Keywords: *Lab; Scale; Teaching Optimization; Practical Teaching; GTA.*

ABSTRACT

Multidisciplinary Engineering Education (MEE) is a specialist department at the University of Sheffield, dedicated to the practical teaching of all the University's engineering students. To deliver this, MEE has a unique building comprising workshops, study spaces, and most importantly 16 laboratories offering a spectrum of lab activities to a population of approximately 4000 students.

Effectively managing our resources (staff, equipment, lab space) is challenging due to the heavy demand of student numbers, but an effective approach allows at-scale teaching while ensuring the institutional vision of teaching excellence.

¹ *Corresponding Author*

M Di Benedetti

m.dibenedetti@sheffield.ac.uk

This paper presents the approaches used to optimise the “Cantilever Truss” activity, taking place in the MEE Structures Lab. Over the last 5 years, several key stakeholders helped develop this activity’s efficiency and scalability which include academics, technicians, MEE’s timetabling manager and teaching assistants.

The key factors in developing the activity were; tuning the learning outcomes for transferability across 3 major courses, optimising the activity tasks for constructive alignment, cross-departmental timetable management, and specialised training for the teaching assistants.

The improvements are measured by several teaching design parameters (teaching hours, student numbers, lab “up-time”, cross-disciplinarity), and considered alongside information gathered from teacher reflection forms as well as informal student feedback. This paper discusses how the approaches used have yielded value in optimisation and improvement, before suggesting general elements that could be useful ‘take-aways’ for different contexts and institutions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Faculty of Engineering at the University of Sheffield attracts hundreds of new students every year. With an increasing student population, large lecture theatres hosting up to 400 students make at-scale lecturing possible. However, it is not economically viable to have sufficiently large laboratories to support at-scale *practical* teaching. For example, one of the larger teaching labs for engineering at Sheffield (Structures Lab) has an actual capacity of 40 students. The labs (16 in total) are all housed in a state-of-the-art specialist department, Multidisciplinary Engineering Education (MEE) which is dedicated to practical teaching [1]. The limitation on lab capacity is overcome by repetition so that lab activities get delivered repeatedly until all the students in a given cohort have worked through them. For example, with a 200-student cohort, it would take 5 sessions for the cohort to complete one activity. To scale up this process, it is essential to optimise the use of resources (i.e., increase student numbers, minimise staff hours, maximise lab space and equipment usage) [2] while introducing appropriate quality control measures to ensure teaching excellence [3]. In particular, this study presents the gradual actions taken over 5 years to scale up the “Cantilever Truss” lab, focusing on three areas of intervention: the lab activity, timetable/resource management, and quality control.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Teaching Activity

The “Cantilever Truss” lab teaches students (first year, first semester) the basics of load paths and load distribution within a simple truss structure. The optimisation process of this lab was guided by the constructive alignment philosophy [4] thus ensuring that all intended learning outcomes (ILOs) were catered for in the teaching/learning activities (TLAs). With this in mind, ILOs and TLAs were finely tuned, and the redundant or ineffective elements were removed. “To demonstrate the Principle of Superposition, as applied to forces and deflections of linear systems” was

one of the original ILOs in 2017. However, a review of the programme material showed that students would not cover “deflection of elastic members” in lectures before the time the lab was scheduled. Dropping the “deflection” component of this ILO ensured better alignment between lab and lecturing material. This also meant students would not need to take deflection measurements, resulting in a significant reduction in the session time. To further reduce session time and to support student engagement, highly repetitive elements of the TLA were dropped. For example, the number of times students applied a load and took internal force readings was halved (from 10 to 5 repetitions) while still gathering a sufficient dataset to draw analogue conclusions. The optimised session time was pursued over the years via trial and reflection. ILOs deemed as low value (“Use a spreadsheet to collect data”) were also removed to focus on the core theoretical ILOs (“Qualitatively determine the distribution of internal forces in a truss structure”). In addition, online digital learning (pre-lab activities including a mandatory quiz) was employed to ensure that students arrived well prepared for more efficient working.

Once the TLA was sufficiently streamlined for Civil and Structural Engineers, it was advertised cross-departmentally. Due to the large overlap of basic concepts across several disciplines, the Mechanical, Aerospace, and General Engineering Departments each decided to include this TLA within their programmes.

2.2 Management

Since MEE opened in 2015 it has served across departments and disciplines in the engineering faculty. Initially, individual departments would dictate MEE weekly lab slots (a slot is “Monday p.m.” or “Thursday a.m.” for example) which often resulted in clashes or having to run the same activity over consecutive weeks, inefficiently. This, in turn, meant that lab time was largely spent being idle or setting up/taking down rather than teaching. To make labs more efficient, in 2021 MEE started timetabling the weekly lab slots for all departments, based on which of the MEE labs each department would primarily use. This averted potential clashes and allowed all departments to use the same lab within a *single* week, greatly minimising downtime.

2.3 Quality Control

The delivery of at-scale teaching in MEE hinges upon Graduate Teaching Assistants (GTAs), which make teaching high numbers of students possible with limited academic staff. To ensure excellence in teaching is retained despite the cyclical turnover of the employed GTAs, a new GTA training system was introduced in 2018 [5]. This training method supports GTAs ongoing pedagogical development and provides lab-relevant technical training.

3 RESULTS

Table 1 shows key data regarding the delivery of the Cantilever Truss lab over the last 5 years and their projection for the future.

Table 1. Teaching Delivery Data for the Cantilever Truss Lab

Year	Number of Modules	Teaching		Sessions		Teaching time (hr)	Lab usage (%)	Timetabled number of students	Students taught per-hour
		weeks	days	Number of	duration (hr:mm)				
2017	1	2	2	3	3:00	9	56	180	20
2018	1	2	3	5	2:00	10	42	120	12
2019	3	2	5	16	1:30	24	60	640	26
2020*	4	2	8	44	1:15	55	86	880	16
2021	5	1	5	23	1:30	34.5	86	920	26
Future	≥5	1	5	28	1:15	35	88	1120	32

* In 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the lab capacity was reduced to 20 students.

The optimisation of the TLA allowed for more than halving the session duration. Observing students suggested that this intervention was pedagogically effective as shorter sessions promoted students' focus and engagement. On the other hand, overly-short sessions (2020/21) caused the slower groups to struggle to complete all TLAs, potentially impacting students' achievement of the ILOs.

The centralised timetabling management was instrumental to the broader incorporation of the activity in different programmes (5 modules) as well as to the improved utilisation of the lab space. In 2021, 23 Cantilever Truss lab sessions were taught in just 5 days of a single week, maximising the teaching time (86% of the total weekly slot time was used) and minimising set-up and downtime.

In addition, the number of students taught increased more than fivefold (180 to 920) while the number of students per academic hour increased by 30% (20 to 26). This suggests that the implemented strategies were highly effective at scaling up teaching, with a secondary benefit to the usage efficiency of staff time. The drawback of having more students is the increased teaching load on staff. This was mitigated by employing more GTAs per session (up to 4). The introduction of a professionalising GTA training allowed staff to delegate teaching delivery without impacting its quality.

In the future, to accommodate a growing student population, this lab activity could be further streamlined and potentially delivered to over 1100 students in a week.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The Cantilever truss lab represents a 5-year process to scale up practical engineering teaching using lab activities. Some elements herein implemented for the Structures Lab will be employed by other MEE labs in the future.

- Teaching activity: minimising redundancy and promoting engagement.
- Management: streamline timetabling to maximise lab usage.
- Quality control: increase skilled teaching capacity by employing and training GTAs.

The philosophy underpinning such elements could be transposed to different contexts and used as a guideline also by other institutions aiming to develop their lab teaching.

REFERENCES

- [1] Judge, M. (2017), Large-scale laboratory teaching for 1st year EEE undergraduates. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*, Vol. 54, No. 2, pp.164-177.
- [2] Garrard, A. and Beck, S. (2018), Pedagogical and cost advantages of a multidisciplinary approach to delivering practical teaching. In *The Interdisciplinary Future of Engineering Education*, Routledge, pp. 33-48.
- [3] French, A. and O'Leary, M. (2017), *Teaching excellence in higher education: Challenges, changes and the teaching excellence framework*. Emerald Group Publishing.
- [4] Biggs, J. & Tang, C. Chapter 6 'Constructively Aligned Teaching and Assessment' of *Teaching for Quality Learning at University*. Fourth Edition, McGraw Hill, 2011.
- [5] Di Benedetti, M., Plumb, S. and Beck, S.B., (2022), Effective use of peer teaching and self-reflection for the pedagogical training of graduate teaching assistants in engineering. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, pp.1-16.